

Effect of Soil Organic Matter (SOM) Content on True Particle Density and other Physical Properties of Sudan Savannah Entisols

Abba Nabayi¹, Abubakar Halilu Girei¹,
Nafiu Garba Hayatu², Jamilu Garba³
and Hassan Aliyu Santuraki¹

¹Department of Soil Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Federal University Dutse, Jigawa state, Nigeria. Ibrahim Aliyu bye-pass. PMB 7156. Dutse, Jigawa state.

²Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Engineering, Faculty of Agriculture, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. PMB 2346 Sokoto state, Nigeria.

³Department of Soil Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. Kaduna State. Nigeria.

Corresponding Author: Abba Nabayi, e-mail: abba.nabayi@fud.edu.ng

Received: 3 May 2021

Accepted: 1 October 2021

Abstract

The study aimed to determine the effect of long-term cultivation and soil organic matter (SOM) content on the particle density (Pd) and other physical properties of an Entisols in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teachings and Research farm. Soil samples were taken from six different spots (A, B, C, D, E, and F) at the depth of 0-15 and 15-30 cm. The field experiment was laid in RCB design and replicated three times each at a depth, totalling 36 samples. Purposive random sampling was used at 50 m intervals from one spot to another. The results show that interaction between sampling spots and sampling depths of the soil was significant ($p < 0.05$) in terms of total porosity (TP), SOM content, bulk density (Bd), and Pd. Averagely, there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm in terms of TP, Bd, and SOM content with the higher values of TP and OM observed in the 0-15 cm depth. The results show that spots near the shelterbelt (C and E) had higher OM, TP, and lower Bd and Pd. In terms of the textural class, differences were also observed among the sampling spots with C and E having sandy loam while the remaining spots had sand texture. Pd was higher in lower OM spots (A, B, D, F). The study revealed that whenever the standard Pd value (2.65 Mg m^{-3}) was used to calculate TP of the soil, particularly spot C and E, it is being overestimated by 2-3%. It is therefore recommended that OM and crop residues should be incorporated and returned immediately after harvesting to help improve the soil properties. When soil is rich in OM, it is recommended that constant value (2.65 Mg m^{-3}) should not be used to calculate its porosity, but rather the actual (measured) Pd of the soil.

Keywords: bulk density, microorganisms, porosity, sandy texture

Introduction

Long-term cultivation tends to lower total porosity because of a decrease in SOM and large peds (Brady & Weil, 2002). The importance of soil organic matter includes an increase of aggregate stability, improving water infiltration and soil aeration, and improves water holding capacity by reducing run-off (Rawls et al., 2004; Kuo & Jończyk, 2008). Mikha et al. (2006) reported that addition of OM to the soil can decrease bulk density (Bd) and increase water holding capacity and soil aggregate stability effectively. Carter et al. (2002) noted that the amount of water-stable aggregates was often associated with soil organic carbon (SOC) content, and carbon was often positively related to macro-aggregate stability. The physical decline in OM content is manifested by a decrease in large pore space, a decrease in wet aggregate stability and an increase in Bd (Kuo & Jończyk, 2008). Savannah soils are mostly predominated by sandy soils (Jones & Wild, 1975).

Soil physical properties are responsible for the transfer of air, heat, solute, and water through the soil (Nabayi et al., 2019a; Zaibon et al., 2016). Several physical properties can and do change because of management practices adopted on a particular land (Borken & Matzner, 2009). Many soil physical properties degenerate due to continuous cultivation, which renders the soil more susceptible to erosion losses and run-off and less permeable (Sanchez, 1976). Therefore, reliable measurement on a volumetric basis instead of assumption is required for the soil physical properties such as TP, Pd, rate of soil particle sedimentation, thermal conductivity, and heat capacity (Hillel, 1998). The above mentioned are Pd-based parameters, which are vital in modelling and understanding various processes, including air, water, heat flow, and chemical transport through the soil. Such importance of Pd in many applications necessitates an accurate measurement of this soil physical property.

Pd is defined as the density of the soil particles collectively which is one of the basic physical properties of soils (Ruehlmann, 2020). Mathematically it is expressed as the ratio of the soil particles' total mass to their total volume, excluding the pore spaces between particles (Brady, 1990). Soil minerals weigh much more per unit volume than OM (Rawls et al., 2004). Soils with higher OM content had lower Pd than soil similar in textures with low OM (Creswell & Hamilton, 2002; Ruehlmann & Körschens, 2020). Soil Pd generally increases with soil depth because of the concurrent decreases in OM (London, 1991). Pd differs from the type of soil mineral present, as well as the amount of OM. The Pd of most mineral soils is assumed to be 2.65 Mg m^{-3} , but when appreciable amount of magnetite and heavy minerals are present, the soil Pd is greater than 2.65 Mg m^{-3} (Brady & Weil, 2002).

Soils formed in volcanic parent materials such as ash generally had Pd less than 2.65 Mg m^{-3} (Blanco-conqui et al., 2006). London (1991) stated that the actual values of Pd depend upon the mineralogical and chemical composition and degree of hydration of the particles. Zero tillage practice decreased soil Pd compared to mouldboard ploughing because of an increase in SOM (Blanco-conqui et al., 2006). The authors (Blanco-conqui et al., 2006) reported that under these circumstances, if the standard value of Pd is used to calculate TP of the soil, then it is overestimated by 12%. Therefore, they concluded that while a Pd of 2.65 Mg m^{-3} can be accurate for some soils, differences in the compositions of solids, such as an increased SOC concentration, can considerably lower the Pd value since OM fraction is an essential component of soil solid.

Cropping system and tillage influence the Pd significantly, and most importantly, the changes in SOC concentration resulting from these management systems primarily modify the Pd of the soil (Singh et al., 1994). Meanwhile, the conversion of traditional tillage to reduced and zero tillage systems increases soil organic carbon pools (Allmaras et al., 2004; Lal, 2004; Hooker et al., 2005; Nabayi et al., 2019b). The Pd is not, however, routinely measured during soil characterization because it is considered to be a constant value of 2.65 Mg m^{-3} , which ranged between 2.60 and 2.70 Mg m^{-3} of the most quartz-dominated soils (Blanco-conqui et al., 2006). The lack of Pd measurement in many soil studies could relate to the rather laborious measurement procedure (Blake & Hartge, 1986). However, OM is one of the important soil parameters that change Pd (Schjønning et al., 2017). The soil management practices put in place can change the soil densities easily (Adams, 1973; Singh et al., 1994). Soil physical properties such as porosity, Bd and hydraulic conductivity are Pd dependent, hence the need for Pd to be measured as a routine soil properties measurement to prevent over and or underestimation of these properties. Soils that are subjected to tillage, and soils that are receiving organic amendments year in year out are particularly susceptible to change in Pd (Nabayi et al., 2019c). The effects of soil organic carbon increases on Pd have not been well documented, and the general assumption is that changes in Pd are negligible (Blanco-conqui et al., 2006; Ruehlmann & Körschens, 2020; Schjønning et al., 2017). The objective of this research was to determine the effect of long-term cultivation and SOM content on true Pd and other physical properties of Usmanu Danfodiyo University teachings and research dryland farm, Sokoto, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Experimental site

The study location was Usmanu Danfodiyo University teachings and research dryland farm, Sokoto, Nigeria. The farm is located within the university premises near Dundaye district, in Wamakko Local Government, Sokoto state on latitude $13^{\circ} 02^1 \text{ N}$ and longitude $5^{\circ} 02^1 \text{ E}$. The soils of the study area were predominantly sandy and had low OM content. The study site falls within the Sudan savannah agroecological zone, which comprises of scattered trees and sparse vegetation. The dominant crops being cultivated on the farm for an extended period are cereals and legumes. The mean annual rainfall ranges between 500-700 mm, and it rains between June and October. Also, the mean annual temperature is greatly variable, ranging from 15° C to 40° C (SERC, 2010).

Treatments, Experimental Design, Samples Collection and Preparation

The sampling spots (A, B, C, D, E, and F) and sampling depths (0-15 and 15-30 cm) were considered as the first and second factor respectively, which were replicated in triplicate each and arranged in a Randomized Complete Block (RCB) design in a factorial arrangement. These consisted of twelve (12) soil samples from the two (2) depths, which are 0-15 cm and 15-30 cm, respectively replicated three (3) times, making a total of thirty-six (36) soil samples. A purposive random sampling technique was used in selecting the spots at 50 m intervals. The soil samples were taken using auger and cores (5 x 5 cm) which were labelled and taken to the laboratory, air dried, grounded and sieved ($< 2 \text{ mm}$) then stored in clean bottle before analysis. Samples for the determination of bulk density were left undisturbed in the core samplers which were oven-dried at 105° C for 24 hours.

Figure 1: Field layout and sampling spots

Determination of Physical Properties

Particle size was determined using the Bouyoucos hydrometer method; where sodium hexametaphosphate (Calgon) was used as a dispersant agent (Gee & Bauder, 1986). The USDA textural triangle was used to determine the textural class of the soil samples.

Particle density was determined using the Pycnometer bottle method (Heiskanen, 1992) from the two measured quantities, namely; a mass of the samples and its volume. The mass was determined by the mass and density of water displaced by the sample.

$$\text{Particle density } (D_p) \text{ (Mg m}^{-3}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Mass of Soil solid (M}_s\text{)}}{\text{Volume occupied by the soil solid (V}_s\text{)}} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Bulk density was measured using the core method, where undisturbed samples were taken in a core of a constant and known volume (Blake & Hartge, 1986). Bulk density of the samples was calculated from the ratio of the oven-dried mass at 105 °C for 24 hours to the

field volume of the soil as given by the volume of the core sampler as described by Blake and Hartge (1986).

$$\text{Bulk density (Mg m}^{-3}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Weight of oven-dried soil sample at 105}^{\circ}\text{C}}{\text{Total Volume of fresh soil sample}} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Porosity was determined indirectly from the measured bulk density and particle density values and using the equation below (Baver et al., 1972);

$$\text{Total porosity} = 1 - \left(\frac{\text{Bulk density}}{\text{Particle density}} \right) \times 100 \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Determination of Organic Matter Content

Walkley-Black wet combustion method was employed in Organic carbon determination in which the soil samples were treated with standard $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and Conc. H_2SO_4 and was titrated with standard ammonium sulphate solution ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$). After Organic Carbon, has been determined, the result was multiplied by a factor 1.72 to get the organic matter content of the soil (Jones, 2001).

Data Analyses

All data collected were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and analysed using Statistical Analyses System (SAS 9.4 SAS system for windows by SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA). Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significant treatment effect on the measured properties with a significant difference of $p < 0.05$. Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used for mean separation.

Results and discussion

Soil Organic Matter (SOM) Content of the Soils

The interaction between sampling spots (SS) and sampling depth (SD) on the OM was significant ($p < 0.001$) and is shown in Figure 2a. The interaction between the SS and SD differed significantly ($p < 0.001$) from one SS to another with the highest (2.1%) in spot E at 0-15 cm while the lowest was obtained in spot D at 15-30 cm depth with 1.43%. Spot E had an increase of 32% of OM than spot D. Higher OM was recorded in spot E than other SS irrespective of the SD. The increase in OM over other SS ranged from 6.1-32%. The mean values of the sampling spots differed significantly from one sampling spot to another in the order of $\text{E} > \text{C} > \text{F} > \text{B} > \text{A} > \text{D}$ with E having an increment of 5.1%, 17.5%, 18%, 18.5%, and 20.6% of OM over C, F, B, A, and D, respectively (Table 1). As indicated in Figure 1, spot C was also near a shelterbelt, which could be attributed to the relatively higher OM content of the spot. Spot E was found to differ significantly ($p < 0.05$) from spot C with only 6.1% which was the least of the differences when compared with other SS. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between spots A, B, D and F at 0-15 cm. Non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference between the spots (A, B, D and F) depicted the clear condition of the farm in terms of OM content, because there was no external influence, as is the case in spots C and E that are continually being influenced by forest leaf litters from the nearby trees. No significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed from spots C and E at 15-30 cm depths, but they differed from their counterpart SS at the same depths. Averagely, significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) OM was found in the upper depth (0-15 cm), which differs from the lower depth (15-30 cm), with 12.2% increased (Table 1). The study agrees with Liebig et al. (2005) and Nabayi et al.

(2019c), who found greater soil organic carbon at the upper depth of 0-5 cm depth when compared to the lower depth. It also agrees with Creswell and Hamilton (2002) who reported that OM weighs much less per unit volume than soil minerals; soil high in organic matter have lower particle density than soil similar in texture but low in organic matter. Hillel (1998) reported that organic matter is an important component of soil solid, which directly influences the physical and hydraulic properties of soil. Organic matter, which is usually in small quantity in soil, has a profound influence on the physical and chemical properties of mineral soils (Blanco-conqui et al., 2006). It promotes the formation and stability of soil structure and increases water retention, infiltration, and drainage (Koorevaar et al., 1983).

Table 1. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and main effect means for organic matter, bulk density, particle density and total porosity. Main effects are sampling spots and sampling depth

<i>ANOVA P>F</i>				
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>OM</i>	<i>Pd</i>	<i>Bd</i>	<i>TP</i>
Replication (R)	.204	.267	.353	.936
Sampling spot (SS)	.001	<.001	<.0001	.013
Sampling depth (SD)	.001	.100	<.0001	.001
SS*SD	.001	.011	.002	.146
<i>Sampling spots</i>		Means		
A	1.58c	2.638b	1.438a	45.5ab
B	1.59c	2.640b	1.438a	46.2ab
C	1.84b	2.626c	1.411c	46.0ab
D	1.54d	2.653a	1.435ab	46.3ab
E	1.94a	2.625c	1.40d	46.5a
F	1.60c	2.631bc	1.42b	45.2b
<i>SE (±)</i>	<i>0.04</i>	<i>0.003</i>	<i>0.009</i>	<i>0.33</i>
<i>Sampling depth (cm)</i>		Means		
0-15cm	1.80a	2.63a	1.40b	46.7a
15-30cm	1.58b	2.64a	1.44a	45.2b
<i>SE (±)</i>	<i>0.03</i>	<i>0.002</i>	<i>0.004</i>	<i>0.19</i>

Mean comparisons were made only when *P* values for the main effects were ≤ 0.05 . Means followed by different letters within the same column differ significantly from one another at 5% level of significance.

Effect of SOM on Particle Size Distribution of the Soils

Table 2 shows that the soil of the dryland farm is predominantly sandy in texture across the SS at different SD. At the depth of 0-15cm, the SS had a range of sand, silt, and clay of 93-96%, 1-2%, and 2-5%, respectively, with a textural class of sand. At 15-30 cm depth, the soils had a range of 81-91% sand, 2-7% silt, and 6-13% clay, with a textural class of sandy loam. All the SS at 15-30 cm SD were found to be sand apart from spots C and E, which were sandy loam in texture. Differences in textural class observed in spots C and E was attributed to the higher OM content obtained in the SS (Figure 2a), and this was due to their proximity to the shelterbelt. The forest litters from the shelterbelt had influenced the texture of some part of the farm to the extent of altering the textural class of the soil, particularly spots C and E. The two SS (C and E) had the highest content of clay (C=12%, E= 13%), silt (C= 6%,

E= 7%) but least in sand percentages when compared with the other SS (Table 2). The result agrees with Jones and Wild (1975), who reported that soils in savannah are predominantly sandy.

Table 2. Means of Particle Size Distribution and Textural Class of the Spots at Different Depths

<i>Particle size distribution</i>	<i>Sand (%)</i>		<i>Silt (%)</i>		<i>Clay (%)</i>		<i>Textural class</i>	
	0-15 cm	15-30 cm	0-15 cm	15-30 cm	0-15 cm	15-30 cm	0-15 cm	15-30 cm
A	96 ^a	89 ^a	2 ^a	5 ^a	2 ^b	6 ^{bc}	Sand	Sand
B	96 ^a	91 ^a	2 ^a	2 ^b	2 ^b	7 ^b	Sand	Sand
C	93 ^a	81 ^b	2 ^a	6 ^a	5 ^a	13 ^a	Sand	Sandy Loam
D	94 ^a	91 ^a	2 ^a	2 ^b	4 ^a	7 ^b	Sand	Sand
E	95 ^a	81 ^b	2 ^a	7 ^a	3 ^{ab}	12 ^a	Sand	Sandy Loam
F	95 ^a	90 ^a	2 ^a	2 ^b	3 ^{ab}	8 ^b	Sand	Sand
<i>SE (±)</i>	1.33	0.67	0.30	0.3	0.44	0.33		

Means followed by the same letters within the same column are not significantly different from each other at 5% level of significance according to DMRT.

Effect of SOM on True Particle Density (D_p) of the Soils

The result of the main and interaction effects of SS and SD on Pd is presented in Table 1. The SS and SD interaction on Pd was significant ($p < 0.01$) and is shown in Figure 2b. The mean values of the particle size analysis, Pd, Bd, and TP at the two different SD is presented in Table 3. The highest Pd was recorded in spot D (2.66 Mg m^{-3}) at 0-15 cm which differed significantly ($p < 0.01$) from other SS, while the lowest was recorded in spots C and E with 2.62 and 2.61 Mg m^{-3} , respectively at 0-15 cm SD. Higher Pd is an indication of low OM content of the soil been part of the soil solid (Schjøning et al., 2017). The results agree with OM results in Figure 2a, which indicated that spot D at 15-30 cm had the least OM content (1.43%) than its other SS counterparts. The low OM in spot D was translated into significantly higher Pd than the other SS irrespective of the SD. Spot D had an increase of 2% of Pd over spot C been the SS (D and C) with the highest and the lowest Pd. The mean values of the Pd differed significantly ($p < 0.01$) from one another in the order of $D > B > A > F > C > E$ with D having an increment of 0.7%, 1.0%, 1.1%, 1.2% and 1.3% of Pd over B, A, F, C, and E, respectively. SD wise, there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in terms of Pd with the higher Pd value in the 15-30 cm and lower in the 0-15 cm, as shown in Table 3. The result agrees with London (1991) and Brady and Weil (2002) who reported that soil particle density generally increases with soil depth because of the concurrent decreases in organic matter. Changes in soil particle density take a longer time to occur, and it depends on the management activities been carried out on a particular soil (Blanco-conqui et al., 2006).

Figure 2. Effect of Sampling spots and sampling depths on (A) organic matter, (B) particle density, (C) bulk density and (D) total porosity of a dryland soil. Bars indicate the standard error. Means with same letters are not significantly different according to DMRT at 5%.

Therefore, the differences observed from one spot to another in the present study were attributed to the location differences. Spots C and E have benefitted to the presence of the shelterbelt which improved the OM of the soil area thereby making the density of the soils to be less, and this agrees with Schjønning et al. 2017 and Ruehlmann and Körschens (2020) who stated that type of soil mineral present and amount of OM affects the Pd of an area.

Table 3. Means (\pm SE) of True Particle Density and other Physical Properties of the Soils

<i>Physical properties</i>	<i>0-15 cm</i>	<i>15-30 cm</i>
Sand (%)	95 \pm 0.70 ^a	87 \pm 1.67 ^b
Silt (%)	2 \pm 0.04 ^b	4 \pm 0.50 ^a
Clay (%)	3 \pm 0.33 ^b	9 \pm 1.00 ^a
Textural class	Sand	Loamy sand
Particle Density (Mg m ⁻³)	2.63 \pm 0.08 ^a	2.64 \pm 0.01 ^a
Bulk density (Mg m ⁻³)	1.40 \pm 0.007 ^b	1.45 \pm 0.01 ^a
Porosity (%)	47 \pm 0.33 ^a	45 \pm 0.03 ^b
Organic matter (%)	1.78 \pm 0.08 ^a	1.59 \pm 0.06 ^b

Means with same letters across the same row are not significantly different from each other at 5% level of significance according to DMRT.

Effect of SOM on Bulk Density (Bd) of the Soils

The main effects of SS and SD is presented in Table 1. The results showed that there was a significant effect of SS and SD, as well as their interaction on the soil Bd ($p < 0.01$). The result of the interaction (Figure 2c) showed that higher Bd values were obtained in spots A, B, and D at 0-15 cm with 1.45, 1.46, and 1.46 Mg m⁻³ each, respectively, while the lowest was found in spots C and E at 0-15cm. Spots C and E had a Bd of 1.39 and 1.38 Mg m⁻³, which differ significantly ($p < 0.01$) from other SS irrespective of the SD. Spots A, B, and D had a Bd increment of 5.5% over spots C and E. Similar to Pd results, OM had influenced the Bd of the soil with spots C and E been richer in OM with a consequent reduction in their soil densities. Table 3 also shows that averagely, there was a significant difference ($p < 0.01$) between the two SD. The higher Bd was recorded at the 15-30 cm with a 2.7% increment over its 0-15 cm counterpart. The higher Bd is equally attributed to the OM contents of the depths with higher OM in the upper depth (0-15 cm), which rendered the soil low in Bd. This result agrees with Han et al. (2006) and Nabayi et al. (2019b), who observed that increases in organic matter content leads to lower bulk density (Bd) of a soil. The result also is in line with research findings by Zaibon et al. (2016), who reported higher Bd with an increase in depth. Variation in Bd was attributed to the relative proportion and specific gravity of solid organic and inorganic particles and the porosity of the soil (Hossain et al., 2015). Similarly, Bd increases with an increase in depth due to consequent reduction in porosity (Creswell & Hamilton, 2002).

Effect of SOM on Total Porosity (TP) of the Soils

The main effects of SS and SD on TP is presented in Table 1. The result of interaction between the SS and SD on TP was significant ($p < 0.001$) and is shown in Figure 2d. The result showed that the highest was recorded in spots B and D at 0-15 cm, each with 47%, which did

not differ significantly ($p>0.05$) from spots C and E at the same depth. The lack of significant difference between the spots was due to the higher Pd and Bd of spots B and D and lower Pd and Bd of spots C and E, as shown in Figure 2b and 2c. The amount of pore space is determined largely by the arrangement of the solid particle (Nabayi et al., 2017). The interaction results indicated a lower TP in virtually all the SS at 15-30 cm with the exception of spot E at the same SD, which had a 2.1% increase over its SD counterpart. However, there was no significant difference ($p>0.05$) between all the SS at 15-30 cm SD despite recording (spot E) higher than its counterpart. The improvement in the TP in the sampling spots C and E despite lower Pd values (Figure 2b) than their counterparts was due to the concurrent decreased in the Bd of the sampling spots because to the higher OM content of the spots.

Table 4. Correlation matrix table for the measured soil physical properties at 0-15 and 15-30 cm soil depths

0-15 cm						
	Bd	Pd	TP	OM	SND	CLAY
PD	0.833*					
PR	-0.600 ns	-0.110 ns				
OM	-0.978***	-0.916*	0.488 ns			
SND	0.492 ns	0.268 ns	-0.442 ns	-0.476 ns		
CLAY	-0.492 ns	-0.268 ns	0.442 ns	0.476 ns	-1.000***	
15-30 cm						
	Bd	Pd	TP	OM	SND	CLAY
PD	0.485 ns					
PR	-0.807*	-0.200 ns				
OM	-0.798 ns	-0.625 ns	0.666 ns			
SND	0.805 ns	0.388 ns	-0.625 ns	-0.935**		
CLAY	-0.743 ns	-0.307 ns	0.530 ns	0.875*	-0.945**	

*Significant at 5%, **Significant at 1%, ***Significant at 0.1%

Bd-Bulk density, Pd-Particle density, TP-Porosity, OM-Organic matter, SND-Sand.

The higher the Bd, the lower the TP and vice versa, but this is only applicable when using a constant Pd for the estimation of soil TP. The results also stressed the importance of including Pd measurement into routine analyses of physical properties because using a constant value may lead to a wrong assumption. Averagely, the main effect of SD shows that the higher TP was obtained in 0-15 cm with 46.7%, which differs significantly ($p<0.01$) from 15-30 cm that had 45.2%. The higher TP in the upper depth (12.2% increased over lower depth) could be attributed to the higher OM of the SD, which differs significantly from the lower depth (Figure 2a). Higher OM content decreases soil density, which in turn increases soil pore spaces (Nabayi et al., 2017). Sanchez (1976) reported that changes in soil structure alter the proportion of the soil pore spaces.

The Pearson correlation also indicate that OM had a significant ($p<0.05$) positive correlation with clay% ($r=0.87$) content at a depth of 15-30 cm (Table 4) but it is negatively correlated with Pd ($r=-0.91$) and Bd ($r=-0.97$) at 0-15 cm depth (Table 4). The result of the correlation indicated that increases in OM content would increase clay content of the soil,

thereby increasing the CEC of the soil in one hand and the increase in OM content would also leads to a decrease in Pd and Bd of the sandy soil on the other hand. The result agrees with Kuo and Jończyk (2008) and Mikha et al. (2006) who reported that increase in TP is among the physical benefits of SOM.

Conclusions

The present study revealed that Pd of a sandy soil particularly dryland farm that is in proximity with shelterbelt- is not a constant value, and therefore, it changes in space and with time depending on the cropping system and the type of soil management practices employed. However, the present study showed that Pd is within the range reported in the literature (2.60-2.70 Mg m⁻³) for sandy soils. Similarly, the study disclosed that higher Pd of a soil is an indication of lower TP and higher Bd as well. On the one hand, OM greatly influenced Pd and other physical properties of the soils as the SS with higher OM shown to have lower Pd, Bd, and higher TP. The negative correlations between OM with Pd and Bd signifies the importance of OM in improving the soil physical condition of the dryland farm.

Recommendations

The present study, therefore, recommends the inclusion of Pd measurement into a routine soil analysis if soil is suspected or known to be under OM influence (increased) because using the constant value to estimate some soil properties that relate to it, would be under or overestimated. It also further suggests that the addition of organic matter into the soil system in form of crop residues, manure, planting of legumes, and adoption of reduced/zero tillage would help improve the soil properties of the farm.

Acknowledgement

We thank the two anonymous reviewers of a former version of the manuscript for their helpful comments and suggestions.

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

References

- Adams, W.A. (1973). The effect of organic matter on the bulk and true densities of some uncultivated podzolic soils. *Journal of Soil Science*, 24, 10-17.
- Allmaras, R. R., Linden, D. R., & Clapp, C. E. (2004). Corn-residue transformations into root and soil carbon as related to nitrogen, tillage and stover management. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 68, 1366-1375.
- Baver, L. D., Gardner, W. H., & Gardner, W. R. (1972). *Soil Physics*, 4th ed. Wiley & Sons, New York.
- Blake, G.R., & Hartge, K. H. (1986). Bulk density. In: *Methods of soil analysis. Part 1. Physical and mineralogical methods*. A. Klute (ed.). Wisconsin: ASA-SSSA. p. 363-375.
- Blanco-Conqiu, H., Lal, R., Post, W. N., Izaurralde, R. C., & Shipitalo, M. J. (2006). Organic carbon influences on soil particle density and rheological properties. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 70, 1407-1414.

Borken, W., & Matzner, E. (2009). Reappraisal of drying and wetting effects on C and N mineralization and fluxes in soils. *Global Change Biology*, 15(4), 808-824.

Brady, N., & Weil, R. (2002). *The Nature and Properties of Soils*, 13th Edition. Prentice Hall. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey. p. 960.

Brady, N.C. (1990). *The Nature and Properties of Soils*. 10th Edition. Macmillan Publishing Company, New York. p. 280.

Carter, M. R., Skjemstad, J. O., & MacEwan, R. J. (2002). Comparison of structural stability, carbon fractions and chemistry of krasnozems soils from adjacent forest and pasture areas in south-western Victoria. *Australian Journal of Soil Research*, 40, 283-297.

Cresswell, H.P., & Hamilton. (2002). Particle size analysis. In: *Soil physical measurement and interpretation for land evaluation*. N.J. McKenzie, H.P. Cresswell and K.J. Coughlan (eds). CSIRO Publishing: Collingwood, Victoria. p. 224-239.

Gee, G. W., & Bauder, J. W. (1986). Particle-size analysis. *Methods of soil analysis: Part 1—Physical and mineralogical methods*, (methods of soil analysis 1), p. 383-411.

Han, J-L., Jin, F. S., Chan, X-B., Sun, H. Y., & Egashira, K. (2006). Physical and chemical properties of major upland soils in Shandong province of China. *Journal of Faculty of Agriculture Kyushu University*, 51(2), 389-393.

Heiskanen, J. (1992). Comparison of three methods for determining the particle density of soil with liquid pycnometers. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 23(7-8), 841-846.

Hillel, D. (1998). *Environmental soil physics: Fundamentals, applications, and environmental considerations*. Academic press.

Hooker, B. A., Morris, T. F., Peters, R., & Cardon, Z. G. (2005). Long-term effect of tillage and corn stalks return on soil carbon dynamics. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 69, 188-196.

Hossain, M. F., Chen, W., & Zhang, Y. (2015). Bulk density of mineral and organic soils in the Canada's arctic and sub-arctic. *Information Processing in Agriculture*, 2(3), 183-190.

Jones, J. B. (2001). *Laboratory guide for conducting soil tests and plant analysis*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL.

Jones, M. J., & Wild, A. (1975). Soils of west African savannah, maintenance and improvement of their fertility. *Tech. Comm. No. 55 of the commonwealth bureau of soil*, Herpenden, England. p. 246.

Koorevaar, P., Menelik, G., & Dirksen, C. (1983). *Elements of soil physics* (Vol. 13). Elsevier.

Kuoe, J., & Jończyk, K. (2008). Influence of organic and conventional crop production system on some parameters of soil fertility. *Journal of Research and Applied Agricultural Engineering*, 53, 161-165.

Lal, R. (2004). Soil carbon sequestration impacts on global climate change and food security. *Science*, 304(5677), 1623-1627.

Liebig, M. A., Johnson, H. A., Hanson, J. D., & Frank, A. B. (2005). Soil carbon under switchgrass stands and cultivated cropland. *Biomass Bioenergy*, 28, 347-354.

London, J. R. (1991). *Booker Tropical soil manual handbook for soil survey and agricultural land evaluation in the tropics and subtropics*. Paperback edition, Longman Scientific and Technical, New York. p. 474.

Mikha, M. M., Vigil, M. F., Liebig, M. A., Bowman, R. A., McConkey, B., Deibert, E. J., & Pikul, J. L. (2006). Cropping system influences on soil chemical properties and soil quality in the Great Plains. *Renewable Agric Food Systems*, 21, 26–35.

Nabayi, A., Girei, A. H., & Abubakar, M. S. (2019a). Physical and hydraulic properties of soils under a long-term tillage practices in Hadejia Local government area, Jigawa state, Nigeria. *Eurasian Journal of Soil Science*, 8(3), 267-274.

Nabayi, A., Girei, A. H., Usman, S., Abubakar, M. S., Haruna, F. D., Nkereuwem, M. E., & M. M. Musa (2019b). Some selected physical and chemical attributes of a Ustalf under different tillage practices at Dutse, Jigawa State Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science*, 29(1), 62-69.

Nabayi, A., Danmowa, N. M., Hayatu, N. G., Girei, A. H., Santuraki, H. A., Haruna, F. D., & Mahmud, A. T. (2019c). Influence of organic matter on some selected physical and hydraulic properties of a Sudan Savannah Entisols. In: *Understanding Nigerian soils for sustainable food and nutrition, security, and healthy environment*. Proceedings of Soil Science of Nigeria held. Held at College of Agronomy Complex (North Core), University of Agriculture, Makurdi on 14-18th July 2019. 719-725.

Nabayi, A., Onokebhagbe, V. O., Nkereuwem, M. E., Santuraki, H. A., Haruna, F. D., Hayatu, N. G., & Mahmud, A. T. (2017). Modification of some physical and chemical properties under different tillage systems in Hadejia. *Dutse Journal of Agriculture and Food Security*, 5(1), 167-176.

Rawls, W.J., Nemes, A., & Pachepsky, Y. (2004). Effect of soil organic carbon on soil hydraulic properties. *Developments in Soil Science*, 30, 95-114.

Ruehlmann, J. (2020). Soil particle density as affected by soil texture and soil organic matter: 1. Partitioning of SOM in conceptual fractions and derivation of a variable SOC to SOM conversion factor. *Geoderma*, 375, 114542.

Ruehlmann, J., & Körschens, M. (2020). Soil particle density as affected by soil texture and soil organic matter: 2. Predicting the effect of the mineral composition of particle-size fractions. *Geoderma*, 375, 114543.

Sanchez, F. A. (1976). *Properties and management of soil in tropics*. Wiley Inc. Publication New York. p.96.

Schjøning, P., McBride, R. A., Keller, T., & Obour, P. B. (2017). Predicting soil particle density from clay and soil organic matter contents. *Geoderma*, 286, 83-87.

SERC. (2010). Sokoto Energy Research Center Weather Record for 2009, 2010, 2011 and 2012.

Singh, B., Chanasyk, D. S., McGill, W. B., & Nyborg, N. P. K. (1994). Residue and tillage management effects on soil properties of a Typic Cryoboroll Under Continuous Barley. *Soil Tillage Research*, 32, 117-133.

Zaibon, S., Anderson, S. H., Kitchen, N. R., & Haruna, S. I. (2016). Hydraulic properties affected by topsoil thickness in switchgrass and corn–soybean cropping systems. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 80, 1365–1376.